

MELCOR 2.2 iPWR LOCA type accident analysis, PART II: BDBA

M. Malicki^{*}, T. Lind

Paul Scherrer Institut, Forschungsstrasse 111, 5232, Villigen, Switzerland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

iPWR
MELCOR
Accident simulations
LOCA

ABSTRACT

The integrated Pressurized Water Reactor brings many potential improvements for the nuclear industry, such as passive and modular design, which potentially supports reliability and safety. Besides their advantages, passive systems are also more challenging to simulate, and predictions of the complex behavior of the reactor, especially under accident conditions, need to be validated. In the first part of this study, the authors analyzed the thermal-hydraulic response of the iPWR to several design basis accident sequences without entering into the severe accident domain. As a continuation of the investigation, a sensitivity study of the beyond design basis accident scenario was performed and analyzed as described and presented here, part 2 of the study.

A generic iPWR MELCOR 2.2 input deck was developed and used to perform a loss-of-coolant accident (LOCA)-type scenario analysis in which a break is assumed in the chemical and volume control system line. The effect of the elevation of the break and decay heat on accident progression is investigated. This allows the examination of input deck and code reliability under different conditions, from full core uncover to mitigated accidents. Overall, eight cases were calculated in which the break elevation and decay heat were varied, providing knowledge about the modeling of the iPWR design and potential analytical challenges, which was the main goal of this work.

The analyses show that MELCOR 2.2 can model iPWR design and simulate severe accident scenarios with different levels of core degradation. One of the technical insights from this preliminary study was that natural circulation plays a significant role in the late phase of a severe accident when the core is uncovered.

1. Introduction

The Small Modular Reactor (SMR) concepts offer innovative approaches to safety and construction as compared to large light water reactors (Small Modular Reactors, 2021). The high interest in commercializing these new nuclear concepts develops the need for updates in the licensing process and safety analyses, which are key elements of each certification procedure (Small Modular Reactors, 2021). Many SMR designs, such as analyzed in this paper iPWR, rely on proven technology; however, their integrated nature forces the introduction of innovative engineering designs (IAEA, 2022; Reyes, 2011; ASTEC code DBA analysis, 2021). These innovations often rely on natural convection, circulation, or other so-called passive features, which, due to their

nature, are more challenging for available analytical tools. The SASPAM-SA project, under the frame of which this work was done, is designed to address these challenges and to support the European licensing processes of light water SMRs (Mascari, 2022). The project's primary goal is to help transfer knowledge obtained from the classic PWR to support future European iPWRs licensing and analyses with a focus on severe accident simulations¹ (Reyes, 2011).

In this paper, the authors continue the investigation presented in (Malicki and Lind) on modeling and simulating the accident progression in a generic iPWR concept using MELCOR 2.2 integral severe accident code. The generic iPWR concept studied here is a 60MWe, entirely passive unit, equipped with a Helical Steam Generator (HSG), double pressure vessel (reactor and containment pressure vessel, RPV and

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: mateusz.malicki@psi.ch (M. Malicki).

¹ Advanced designs, as iPWRs, are in general characterized by common features with the current operating large-LWR and by other specific features typical of their inherent evolutionary designs, providing safety advantages that reinforce the first three levels of the DiD principle. However, even if a plant is designed with advanced inherent features (through the reinforcement of the 1,2,3 DiD levels) allowing a reduction of the Core Damage Frequency (CDF), independent features for preventing and mitigating a severe accident sequence have to be included in its design (DiD level 4) together with the offsite emergency response (DiD level 5). Therefore, some scenarios that could lead to severe accidents need to be postulated and deterministically studied. More detailed information can be found in (SMR Regulators' Forum, 2018).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2024.113667>

Received 18 April 2024; Received in revised form 15 July 2024; Accepted 22 October 2024

Available online 5 November 2024

0029-5493/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Containment, respectively) submerged into a Reactor Pool (RP), The input deck was developed using the SASPAM-SA database based on publicly available information, and it does not represent any particular design.

Most SMRs aim to increase safety, often achieved through passive safety systems relying on natural convection and reduced equipment and piping. Modeling these passive and interconnected systems can be challenging, especially under severe accident conditions. The passive systems, by definition, do not require any action or external power to work. They rely on pressure, temperature, and density differences; often, these differences are relatively small compared to forces used in active systems (pumps). This makes passive systems simple by design, but sensitive to parameter fluctuations (temperature, pressure). The system and severe accident codes often use coarse nodalization, and simplified models, which bring uncertainties and often parameter fluctuations which, in the case of an active system, could be relatively easy to handle. In passive designs, however, minor parameter discrepancies or mass flow disruption caused by numerical instabilities and fluctuations could lead to system malfunction and misleading results. For example, relatively small changes, e.g., in mass flow rate, can disturb natural circulation patterns or cause temporary reverse flow. In other words, passive systems often rely on relatively small forces (density or pressure difference), which, locally and temporarily, could be easily disturbed.

Many SMRs, e.g., iPWR, do not need electricity to mitigate accidents, which practically excludes Station Black Out (SBO) from analyses. In addition, pressurized vessel-type Containment and reduced amount of piping change the importance of Loss of Coolant Accident (LOCA) scenarios as the Containment is closed coupled with the reactor pressure vessel. These advanced features of iPWR also require exploratory research on severe accident scenario definition and analyses, as the typical PWR approach may not be sufficient.

In most of the available codes used for Design Basis Accident (DBA) and Beyond Design Basis Accident (BDBA) analyses, validation for certain SMR features is limited. The work related to SMR safety simulations is ongoing in many directions, e.g., natural circulation (Lin et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2020; Yifan et al., 2021), floating SMRs (Qiu et al., 2020), or submerged pressurized Containment (Lebel et al., 2022; Santinello and Ricotti, 2018; Santinello et al., 2017). To face those challenges and enhance confidence in SMR / iPWR accident simulations, sensitivity and uncertainty analyses (Hosseini et al., 2021; Qiu et al., 2023) are also used to provide a database about potential issues and to identify gaps in numerical models. Most analytical codes, including MELCOR, were initially designed for larger generation II power plants that rely on active systems. Continuous code development is adapting these tools to address SMR and generation IV reactors, for example, by adding models related to helical steam generators, high-temperature reactors, or accident-tolerant fuel (Humpries and Gauntt, 2018; Humpries, 2017; Humpries, 2018).

This paper presents a hypothetical postulated BDBA scenario analysis of iPWR focusing on evaluating input deck and code reliability. Moreover, performed scenario sensitivity analysis will allow a better understanding of iPWR severe accident phenomenology, concentrating on the importance of natural circulation and the impact of the decay heat on accident progression. The sensitivity analyses aim to highlight analytical challenges, especially the simulation of passive systems, and differences compared to classic PWRs. In this work, MELCOR 2.2 is used as a computational tool similar to Part I, in which the methods are described in more detail (Malicki and Lind).

The presented results contain, a comparison of the timing of selected key transient events between sensitivity cases, and the thermal-hydraulic and accident analyses. The scenario chosen for this study is a LOCA-type scenario in which a break is assumed in the Chemical and Volume Control System line (CVCS) and it leads to the containment vessel. The effect of the break elevation and decay heat on the accident progression is analyzed.

Input deck and iPWR description

The input deck used in this study is described and assessed in part I of this study (Malicki and Lind). To avoid repetition in this paper, the authors only briefly describe the iPWR design and MELCOR2.2 input deck.

The main characteristic of the iPWR studied here is that all components essential for the nuclear island, such as core, hot leg, cold leg, pressurizer, and steam generators, are packed into the RPV. These compact approaches force innovative solutions into civil power plants, e.g., once-through helical steam generators, which enhance heat exchange, efficiently extract heat from the Reactor Coolant System (RCS), and transport energy to the steam turbine. The whole RPV is placed inside a second pressurized steel vessel called Containment Pressure Vessel, which is submerged in the reactor pool and acts as an ultimate heat sink (see Fig. 1). The RCS heat is transferred to the ultimate heat sink due to vapor condensation inside the containment vessel. This iPWR concept has no pumps or active safety injection systems for normal operation or accident conditions. The design relies on convection, natural circulation, and pressure differences. The main safety system used in this study is an Emergency Core Cooling System (ECCS), which is a system of valves that allows circulation of the coolant between RPV and Containment during an accident.

The MELCOR 2.2 input deck developed for this work represents those unique features, such as two pressure vessels and core cooling systems. The proper (detailed) nodalization and input deck arrangement in case of modeling natural circulation flow phenomena is essential to properly resolve and the passive cooling can be modeled. The input deck used was developed to support foreseen natural circulation and temperature stratification, which play a major role in accident progression in

Fig. 1. Schematic design of a generic iPWR, with default elevation of the RRV and break (CVCS line), not in scale.

integrated passive designs such as those analyzed here in iPWR. Defining CVH elevation, HS, and flow path arrangement to mimic expected natural circulation and water/vapour level was a base approach for developing the input deck. It is divided into three regions: RPV, Containment, and reactor pool, see Fig. 1. It should be highlighted that the iPWR and MELCOR input deck is a generic iPWR based on publicly available data, gathered in the SASPAM-SA project. Because of its generality, many simplifications, adjustments, and assumptions were needed to complete the SASPAM-SA database; thus, it should be considered an iPWR-like model, not a particular design (SASPAM-SA, 2023).

The unit is modeled with a power of 160 MW_{th}. In the input deck, the ECCS is modeled as set of valves, i.e., Reactor Recirculation Valves (RRV) from Containment to RPV placed above the elevation of the core, and Reactor Ventilation Valves (RVV) placed on the top of the pressurizer connecting it with Containment. Besides these valves, four additional flow paths connecting RPV with Containment were modeled in the input deck. The pressurizer safety valves at the top of the pressurizer, the lower plenum melt ejection line at the bottom of the lower plenum (necessary in MELCOR in case of melt ejection), and the Chemical and Volume Control System (CVCS) line. The present study assumes a break in the CVCS line. Most of the parameters that were not specified in the project were defined as a MELCOR 2.2 default based on manuals and best practices (Humphries et al., 2019; Humphries et al., 2019; Ross et al., 2014). More details about the iPWR concept and the input deck can be found in Part I of this paper (Malicki and Lind) and our previous studies (Malicki et al., 2024).

2. Steady-state and scenario assumptions

Before the initiating event, a steady state was calculated for 3000 s. The obtained steady-state parameters were sufficiently close to the SASPAM-SA reference (SASPAM-SA, "Milestone 2.1: Generic Data on Design 1 and Design 2", 2023), allowing transient calculations to proceed, as discussed in part I (Malicki and Lind).

The selected transient is a hypothetical postulated severe accident BDBA scenario chosen in the SASPAM-SA project as a part of the iPWR assessment study. The sensitivities analyses of the BDBA done in this study were decided based on internal discussions and similar investigations (Campbell et al., 2019; Malicki et al., 2024; Kima et al., 2011; Li et al., 2017; Fakhraei, 2021). This sensitivity study investigates the impact of the break elevation and decay heat on the results and accident progression. By varying the scenario assumptions, the authors focus on assessing the performance of the input deck and the code models under different accident conditions, which helps provide insights about severe accident simulation capabilities for future iPWR calculations.

A considered BDBA scenario is a LOCA-type transient with a break in the CVCS line combined with a partial safety system failure. In this study, the CVCS line break elevation is varied to assess its effect on the accident progression and evaluate the capability of MELCOR to reproduce the generated natural circulation flows with different break elevations. In this PSI study, the default elevation is assumed in area between top of the core and bottom of SG at ~ 7.3 m from the bottom of the Containment. An additional assumption is a partial ECCS malfunction; both RRVs are stuck closed, which limits the possibility of coolant circulation from the Containment to the RPV. In this scenario, condensate recirculation from Containment back to RPV can happen only through the CVCS break. The break elevation as a sensitivity parameter should significantly change accident progression, allowing investigation of the input deck and code under various conditions. Due to the constant amount of water in the system, the level that condensate could reach on Containment side is limited. Changing break elevation will directly impact i) the time when water starts circulating back to the RPV, and ii) the elevation at which water will stabilize in the RPV. Higher break elevation will allow more water to evacuate from the RPV, thus

gathering more in Containment and delaying recirculation time to the RPV. This might affect the accident progression as coolant recirculation will be limited.

Besides break elevation, the decay heat is used as a sensitive parameter. One of the motivations for considering decay heat as a sensitive parameter is that the whole iPWR relies on natural circulation, which is driven by a balance between heat generated in the core and the cooling capabilities of the entire RCS. The manipulation of heat generated in the core allows for investigation of its impact on the scenario progression and natural circulation performance calculated by MELCOR 2.2. All scenarios presented in this study are labeled and shortly described in Table 1. In the project assumptions and the presented calculations, the cross-section of the break (CVCS line) is about ten times smaller than the design recirculation path RRV. As this is an exploratory study of the generic iPWR concept, the additional assumption in BDBA4 cases has been made to investigate the case where break elevation is defined as the assumed default ~ 7.3 m, but the reverse flow from the Containment to RPV through the break is artificially blocked.

The two decay heats based on ANS73 standards were selected for this calculation. In all cases, decay heat is scaled down to the iPWR power. For the sensitivity study, the nominal decay heat is labeled as ANS, and that is elevated by 20 % as ANS 120 %, see Table 1. All cases were analyzed for 48 h; however, in some cases, only part of the calculations is presented to make the analysis more readable.

3. Results

In this chapter, the authors present analyses of the key parameters for the scenario progression, including the timing of the events, thermal-hydraulic response, and severe accident aspects of the BDBA scenarios. This chapter is divided into several sub-chapters, allowing one to see the influence of the scenario assumptions on the timing/dynamics of main events and analyze variables evolution in time.

3.1. Transient description

The progression of the different BDBA scenarios is similar until the ECCS actuation. In the investigated scenarios, two ECCS valves (RRVs) in the lower-mid part of the RPV malfunctioned by being stuck closed. When operational, RRVs would allow water flow from Containment to RPV. Closed RRVs limit the possibility of water circulation between two pressure vessels. In the BDBA scenarios, the water can circulate between RPV and Containment when reaching the elevation of CVCS (break), which varies between the cases. The list of the major events, safety signals and parameters are presented in Table 2 and Table 3. Overall, the results show that MELCOR calculations give coherent results and, based on the experience from PWR analyses, the expected dynamic of the transient.

When the break occurs, the mixture of steam and water rises in the RPV and is released to Containment through the break, and after ECCS actuation, it is also released through the open RVVs. In the cases with low break elevation, the water evacuates from RPV quicker than in cases with higher break elevation, accelerating the accident at the beginning of the transient, see Table 2, e.g., Water level TAF for BDBA2 and BDBA3. However, in the long term, the cases with a lower break are less severe, with no core uncover and no core degradation. This is because, in these cases, low elevation break leads to less water transfer to the Containment and allows condensed water to circulate back to RPV, which keeps the core covered, see Table 2, e.g., the start of core damage, which occurs in five cases.

BDBA4 cases are different as, in those, the reverse flow from the Containment to the RPV through the break is blocked; thereby, no circulation through the break from Containment to RPV occurs. This assumption was added to investigate an extreme situation in which one vessel dries out (RPV) while all the water inventory is collected in the other vessel (Containment), and there is almost no steam circulation

Table 1
Description of the scenario sensitivity assumptions.

Scenario	CVCS elevation from bottom of Containment [m]	CVCS definition	RVV availability	RRV availability	Decay heat
BDBA1	~7.3	100 % break	available	unavailable	ANS
BDBA1_120					ANS 120 %
BDBA2	~8.3	100 % break	available	unavailable	ANS
BDBA2_120					ANS 120 %
BDBA3	~9.0	100 % break	available	unavailable	ANS
BDBA3_120					ANS 120 %
BDBA4	~7.3	100 % break no reverse flow	available	unavailable	ANS
BDBA4_120					ANS 120 %

Table 2
Comparison of main event timing in BDBA scenarios and other significant accident signatures.

ANS parameter	BDBA1		BDBA2		BDBA3		BDBA4	
	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %
Break opens [s]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCRAM signal [s]	17.7	17.7	17.9	17.9	18.1	18.1	18.0	17.6
High containment water level [s]	341	338	342	340	472	494	341	338
ECCS actuation [s]	341	339	342	341	473	495	342	339
Water level TAF [s]	–	–	4303	3776	5707	5125	4363	3813
Start of H ₂ generation [s]	–	–	27,970	23,420	12,750	10,530	10,740	8910
Start of core damage [s]	–	–	37,100	–	14,865	17,086	15,565	13,105
Water level BAF [s]	–	–	–	–	17,044	14,955	15,602	13,063
Steam circulation [s]	–	–	–	–	20,382	17,382	18,893	15,544
MIN RCS water level [s]	91,201	4315	37,230	41,650	83,292	64,637	76,657	53,247

Table 3
Comparison of selected parameters.

ANS parameter	BDBA1		BDBA2		BDBA3		BDBA4	
	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %
MIN RCS water level [m]	3.07	3.21	1.52	1.43	0.4 (RPV dry)	0.4 (RPV dry)	0.4 (RPV dry)	0.4 (RPV dry)
PCT [K]	607	606	2393	2390	2376	2393	2496	2373
Core damage [%]	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.8	22.6	11.2	100
Total H ₂ [kg]	0	0	69.9	78.5	46.0	58.3	60	64

Fig. 2. Evolution of the BDBA RCS water level (on the left) and Containment water level (on the right).

between these two vessels. The BDBA events analyses in Table 2 show that higher break elevation accelerates mid-long-term severe accident progression (e.g. H₂ generation, see Table 2) and makes transient more severe (higher core degradation). The complete core uncover happened only for BDBA3 and BDBA4 cases in which there was no recirculation of water from Containment to RPV.

In Table 2, steam circulation defines a time when the coolant level drops below the bottom of the lower core support plate, allowing steam to circulate in the whole RCS. The MIN RCS water level cannot drop below about 0.4 m, which in presented input deck is assumed as a bottom of the lower plenum; thus, 0.4 m means that RCS is completely dried out.

3.2. Pressure evolution and water level

It is seen that both decay heat and break elevation have an impact on accident progression. The first and most obvious difference between the BDBA cases is the water level in RCS and Containment, which changes along with break elevation. Fig. 2 presents the water level in RCS (on the left) and Containment (on the right). The figure illustrates the collapsed liquid level, which does not consider an elevated surface due to a potential void in the water. The water levels display an inverse correlation to each other, where a high water level in RCS corresponds to a low level in Containment, and vice versa. This is an obvious consequence of the break elevation, which varies between the cases, and it is caused by the limited water inventory in the RPV at the beginning of the accident. The coolant in the Containment, when it reaches the elevation of the break, starts to circulate back to the RPV through the break. By establishing this circulation, water levels stabilize at a certain level. The water surface in Containment stabilizes around the elevation of the break, in cases where circulation between RPV and Containment is possible, at ~ 7.3 m and ~ 8.3 m, respectively, for a break at ~ 7.3 m (BDBA1) and ~ 8.3 m (BDBA2). In the cases where the break is below 9 m, there is only partial or no core uncover, as enough coolant circulates back from Containment to RPV. In cases in which the break is at ~ 9.0 m, there is not enough water in the Containment to reach the break elevation (BDBA3s) or reverse flow is blocked (BDBA4s). Consequently, there is no coolant circulation from Containment to RPV, and the core gets uncovered, initiating core degradation. In the long term, the RCS level drops to 0.4 m, which is the bottom of the lower plenum (RPV dried out). The decay heat does not impact the coolant level as there is no coolant leakage from the Containment; thereby, the coolant level is determined by the total water inventory in the system.

Analyzing pressure in RCS (pressurizer) and Containment,

Fig. 4. Evolution of the BDBA Containment pressure.

respectively, in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, it is seen that Containment reaches the highest pressure shortly after the break occurs, in around 0.1 h for all cases. From that point, RPV and Containment are in pressure equilibrium. The effect of the break elevation is seen in the evolution of pressure. The pressure decreases rapidly until cladding oxidation starts producing hydrogen BDBA1s cases do not show any pressure increase as the water level stays above the TAF, and there is no cladding oxidation. BDBA2 scenarios show dynamic pressure increases between 10–25 h and then a small drop and stabilization at higher pressures. This is caused by a slight decrease in the water level in the RCS, which stabilizes right above BAF; see Fig. 2. Additionally, the water level in the Containment is high enough to circulate back to RPV. This enhances steam generation, which increases pressure in the system. H₂ generation increases pressure further, which will be discussed in the next section. In BDBA2 cases, the impact of increased decay heat is also the most visible, especially in the middle of the transient. In BDBA3 and BDBA4 cases in which water recirculation from Containment to RPV does not occur, pressures in RPV and Containment drop until 5 h. At this time, the water level in the RPV reaches the BAF, and fast cladding oxidation starts; this causes a pressure peak reaching about 2.0 MPa. After hydrogen generation stops, the pressures gradually decrease and show a relatively stable behavior at around 1.0 MPa for the rest of the calculation until 48 h. In most cases, the stabilization is in the 0.5–1.0 MPa range.

3.3. Hydrogen generation

The coolant circulation between RPV and Containment, and thereby the RPV water level, had a decisive impact on hydrogen generation. The BDBA1 analyses show no H₂ generation as the water level in the RCS remains above the TAF during the whole accident, Fig. 5. All the other analyzed scenarios generated more than 45 kg of hydrogen during the 48 h of analysis. In BDBA2 cases, the pressure increase between 10 h and 25 h, seen in Fig. 3, corresponds to H₂ generation. After 25 h, H₂ generation slows down, and it stops at around 28 h. The observed hydrogen generation is linked to the RCS water level; one can see that BDBA2 cases in which the RCS's water level stabilizes around the bottom of the core generate more H₂ than other cases. This is explained by the fact that in BDBA2s, a large amount of steam is generated and is available for Zr oxidation. Additionally, the natural steam circulation within the RCS is not established as the water level remains above the lower support plate. This blocks circulation flow paths and causes higher cladding temperature and enhanced oxidation.

The BDBA3s cases show a visible impact of the elevated decay heat. In BDBA3, the major fraction of hydrogen, 46 kg, is generated in the first oxidation phase between 4 and 7 h, while in BDBA3_120, H₂ generation

Fig. 3. Evolution of the BDBA RCS pressure.

Fig. 5. Total generation of the H₂.

continues until 25 h, producing a total of 58 kg H₂.

The BDBA4 shows rapid generation of around 60 kg of H₂ caused by fast Zr oxidation around 6 h; see Fig. 5. The BDBA4_120 continuously generates H₂ between 3 and 25 h, with a maximum at the end of the transient being about 64 kg. It looks like the BDBA3 and BDBA4 cases behave similarly to each other, which is also the case for the corresponding cases with elevated decay heat. However, BDBA4 cases generate slightly more H₂ than BDBA3 cases, but as discussed in the next section, they lead to higher core degradation. The difference in H₂ generation between default and elevated decay heat cases could be explained by the slightly higher temperature of the circulating coolant in RCS. In Fig. 6 the vapor temperature in the lower plenum (core inlet) and riser (core outlet) is presented. One can see that BDBA3_120 has higher temperatures until ~ 23 h and BDBA4_120 until ~ 41 h, corresponding to times when H₂ generation significantly slows down in those cases.

3.4. Peak cladding temperature and core degradation

The peak cladding temperature (PCT) in Fig. 7, shows the highest cladding temperature in the entire core, which spike may indicate the time when Zr oxidation starts (as oxidation is a strongly temperature-

Fig. 7. PCT evolution.

dependent phenomenon), thus, the beginning of the core degradation. It is essential to mention that the cladding temperature in MELCOR is not only the temperature of the metallic Zr alloy but also ZrO₂.

In BDBA1s the core is covered throughout the accident, and thereby, no heat-up of the core takes place. In cases where the RPV water level drops below TAF (BDBA2-BDBA4), as the core is at least partially uncovered, the cladding heats up, causing oxidation of Zr cladding, resulting in a temperature increase in the core.

In BDBA2 cases, the temperature peak is delayed compared to the rest and occurs between 11–13 h, as the decrease of coolant level in the core is slow. Even though the PCT in BDBA2s is above 2350 K, it does not lead to core degradation, Fig. 8. One can see that the BDBA2 case generates the most H₂, and one of the highest (on average) PCT but does not lead to severe core degradation. On the other hand, the more rapid and intense oxidation in the BDBA4 case generates much less H₂ than in BDBA2 cases, which is most probably caused by higher steam accessibility in BDBA2s but leads to complete core meltdown. These cases give insights into the scenario analyses and potential consequences of the accident. When decay heat is higher, core degradation starts earlier. Also, when the recirculation of coolant from the Containment to RPV is blocked (BDBA4s), the transient is accelerated relative to other scenarios in which coolant can flow from the Containment to RPV. All this underlines the importance of coolant circulation in the integrated designs

Fig. 6. Vapor temperature in lower plenum (on the left) and riser (on the right).

Fig. 8. Evolution of the core damage parameter, fraction of the core fuel which is no longer intact (core collapse variable COR-DAMAGE).

and its modeling in safety-related codes. This phenomenon is essential for accurate simulation of accident progression as one can see that disturbance of that circulation could be critical for accident evolution.

In BDBA3 and BDBA4 cases, the core gets uncovered between 4–5 h, resulting in a fast increase of temperatures. After the first temperature peak, the core cools down as the steam generation in the RPV provides enough cooling for the core, and there is no more metallic Zr in the hottest part of the core, causing PCT to drop. The cases with elevated decay heat show rapid PCT increase right after the first peak. The PCT timing is strongly correlated with the evolution of core degradation Fig. 8. The PCT drops in BDBA3_120 (22 h) and BDBA4_120 (13 and 26 h) are related to collapsing of the hottest core cells. It happens due to the lost integrity of the cladding, which is a consequence of long-term exposure to high temperatures and oxidation in the surrounding cells. In all mentioned cases, the increased decay heat led to earlier and higher core degradation Fig. 8.

The BDBA4_120 has the highest core degradation. In the first oxidation phase (~4h), the temperature evolution in BDBA4_120 is similar to BDBA4 as well as BDBA3 cases, but in the later phase, temperature evolution is distinctly different from the other analyzed cases. Analyzing PCT (Fig. 7) and core degradation (Fig. 8), one can see that in BDBA4_120, the natural circulation of the gas was not able to cool down the core effectively. One can see that in BDBA4_120 PCT increased and

dropped three times, around 4, 13, and 26 h, confirming that circulation within RCS was insufficient to stabilize the uncovered core. In that case, the core, part by part, was heated up, and when it reached rapid oxidation temperature, the hottest core cells collapsed, causing a temperature decrease, which can be noticed in oxidation peak in Fig. 9. The PCT in Fig. 7 drops to 0 K because there is no more cladding material, so the temperature cannot be calculated. The BDBA4 case, opposite to the BDBA4_120, cools down the core efficiently, keeping PCT around 1000 K till the end of the transient. This difference is probably due to the changed core degradation dynamics in those two cases. Elevated decay heat at the beginning of the accident caused increased circulation, which prevented early core degradation; however, in the later phase, even though the mass flow rate through the core was higher compared to BDBA4, the increased energy in the core enhanced oxidation, which leads to PCT increase and further core degradation.

3.5. Effect of blocked recirculation and decay heat

Steam and H₂ circulation within the RPV (Fig. 10, Fig. 11), and circulation between RPV and Containment (Fig. 12, Fig. 13, and Fig. 14) were investigated to understand the phenomena of the coolant circulation. It should be noted that if the integrated mass flow rate is constant, it means that there is no flow.

The BDBA1 cases show zero H₂ mass flow rate out of the core,

Fig. 10. The integrated total mass of H₂ that flowed through the riser.

Fig. 9. Oxidation heat on the left and its zoom on the right.

Fig. 11. The integrated total mass of steam that flowed through the riser on the left and through the downcomer on the right.

Fig. 12. The integrated total mass of steam that flowed through the CVCS break on the left and RVV1 on the right.

Fig. 13. The integrated total mass of H₂ that flowed through the LOCA on the left and RVV1 on the right.

Fig. 10, and zero steam mass flow rate through the downcomer, Fig. 11. This result is expected as the reactor water level remains above TAF during the whole analysis, and thereby, there is no core uncover and no core degradation.

The BDBA2 cases are similar to BDBA1 as there is no H₂ circulation in

the RCS, but because in those cases, H₂ was generated, the integrated mass flow is not zero but 69–78 kg (see legend in Fig. 10), which means that generated H₂ was transported out from the core and not circulated in the RCS.

The BDBA3 cases present stable H₂ and steam mass flow rates

Fig. 14. The integrated total mass of H_2 that flowed through the RVV1 (zoom-in to y axis range 0–20 kg/s).

through the core. Higher decay heat results in a higher mass flow rate for both gases in both cases. Higher decay heat increases circulation in the RCS due to higher temperature differences in the system. Another observation is that stable steam and H_2 circulation are established when the RCS coolant level drops below the lower support plate (around 5 h), as the integrated values constantly increase.

The BDBA4 behaves very similar to the BDBA3 but with higher mass flow rates for both H_2 and steam. This suggests that lack of RPV-Containment circulation increases internal RPV circulation, which is seen as a higher mass flow rate in the downcomer and core outlet. However, higher decay heat seems to result in the opposite behavior. Interesting behavior is seen in BDBA4_120, in which the steam mass flow rate decreases to almost zero at around 18 h and then increases again after 42 h, Fig. 11. The steam occurrence in the BDBA4_120 case is particularly interesting because there is a limited possibility of the steam flowing back from the Containment to RPV. In the BDBA4_120, the steam flow stops around 5 h before full core degradation. The H_2 mass flow rate also differs; both cases show a visible increase starting from 42 h. The lack of steam circulation could suggest that all steam was evacuated to the Containment or consumed by oxidation, which, taking into account full core degradation, is plausible.

The integrated mass flow rate plots of the Containment-RPV circulation were utilized to increase the clarity of the analyses, and they are presented in Fig. 12, Fig. 13 and Fig. 14. It should be noted that in the figures that present integrated values, the flow is in the design direction if a value increases. For RVV and LOCA flow paths, it means from RPV to Containment. If the integrated value decreases, the flow is in the opposite direction.

RPV/Containment steam and H_2 circulation of BDBA1 and BDBA2 are not presented as they did not calculate significant core degradation due to the high water level in Containment, which allows liquid circulations.

Based on the integrated mass flow rate of the steam flowing through LOCA and RVV1 (RVV2 and RVV3 are similar) in Fig. 12, Fig. 13 and Fig. 14, one can see that in the cases with higher decay heat (visible for BDBA3s) circulation is more stable as LOCA flow decreases and RVV1 flow increases more rapidly which means that steam is going through the RVVs to Containment and circulating back through the break to RPV.

The BDBA4 cases have no reverse flow through LOCA; however, in Fig. 12 one can see that in the BDBA4_120 there is a steam reverse flow through RVV1, which explains the appearance of the steam circulating in the RCS after complete core meltdown ~ 42 h (the oxidation rate decreases at that time, so steam is not consumed), see Fig. 9 and Fig. 11. The reverse flow will be discussed in next section.

The H_2 circulation shows different behavior, but considering

differences in the H_2 generation and core degradation, it is expected. Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 show the cases with higher decay heat after the second oxidation discharge H_2 into the Containment, as in the BDBA4. The general observation is that in the cases where the break reverse flow is not blocked, the H_2 circulation is well established, while in BDBA4s, only minor fluctuations through RVVs occur that can be considered negligible.

The mass flow rates of steam and H_2 discussed above highlight the challenges of the passive phenomena simulations and the sensitivity of the numerical models and input deck to the scenario assumptions. Moreover, based on those observations, it could be concluded that higher decay heat led to faster core degradation. Moreover, if gas circulation is established, the higher decay heat provides higher convective forces, which increase the circulation mass flow rate, affecting accident progression e.g., more constant H_2 generation.

These outcomes underline tool challenges (e.g., mass flow rate fluctuation occurs in natural circulation patterns) and the differences in severe accident modeling, simulation, and analyses between conventional NPPs and iPWRs (e.g., impact of the circulation patterns between RPV and Containment). All those remarks could be helpful in further examination of the integrated designs. Nonetheless, despite all efforts during the input deck preparation, the input deck and simulation uncertainties are relatively high due to many assumptions and simplifications made by the authors and due to the innovative nature of the iPWR concept. Thus, the challenges mentioned above, along with the flow fluctuations, discrepancies between analyzed sensitivities, and the importance of natural convection in iPWR, raise demands to continue the sensitivity and uncertainty study of that topic.

3.6. RCS coolant circulation

To investigate the effect of coolant circulation in RCS on the accident progression, the core degradation against RCS water level and core outlet mass flow rate are presented for BDBA3, and BDBA4 cases, respectively, in Fig. 15, and Fig. 16. The figures represent simplified plots of the variables as, due to high mass flow rate fluctuations, only each 8th plot point is presented to smoothen the graph and increase its readability. The bottom of the lower support plate highlighted in the figures is the level below which steam can circulate through the core; the top of the core is at around 3.5 m. In the figures, we show the link between the variables; thus, minimum (Min) and maximum (Max) values of the parameters are placed in the legends with the timing of the first occurrence (units in the legend correspond to the one on the axis).

In Fig. 15 one can see that in the BDBA3, the mass flow rate of steam is slightly, however visibly, lower than in the BDBA3_120 in contrary to the RCS water level, which is higher for BDBA3. The higher values in BDBA3_120 mass flow rate could be caused by higher average coolant temperature, which enhances convective forces within RCS. The differences in RCS water level are due to quicker coolant evaporation in higher decay heat cases, leading directly to lower coolant levels. Higher decay heat leads to faster water level decrease and, consequently, core degradation (54347 s) shortly before complete dry out (64637 s). The BDBA3 case also calculates core degradation, but minor and only in the first oxidation phase (18095 s). In both analyses, the flow and water level act similarly, but in the BDBA3, the steam mass flow rate fluctuations are higher and more intense than in the BDBA3_120, especially before drying out of RPV.

In all cases with full core uncover (BDBA3s, BDBA4s), the steam mass flow rate at the core outlet increases significantly when the RPV water level drops below the lower support plate, caused by RCS steam and H_2 natural circulation. At that time, the lower plenum (LP) was still filled with water, and RPV was full of steam, leading to the increased flow rate described above. Then, the RCS water level drops to about 0.4 m (bottom of the LP), as the recirculation from the Containment is limited. There is no more steam generation in the RPV, and if residual steam is consumed by oxidation (BDBA4_120), only H_2 circulates in the

Fig. 15. Core degradation comparing with RCS water level and core outlet mass flow rate for BDBA3 cases (smoothed graph).

Fig. 16. Core degradation comparing with RCS water level and core outlet mass flow rate for BDBA4 cases (smoothed graph).

system, as discussed above. In BDBA3s, and BDBA4 analyses after RPV dry out, the steam mass flow rate of around 0.5–1 kg/s stabilizes until the end of the transient. Also, the mass flow rate stabilization in those cases seems to follow RPV dry-out time. At this time, the whole system (RPV- Containment –RP) starts to be in a semi-equilibrium state with steam and H₂ circulation in the RPV and Containment system.

The BDBA4_120 is different; when RPV dries out, the mass flow rate starts dropping and, in a few hours, stabilizes below ~ 0.1 kg/s, Fig. 16. In these cases, the decreasing mass flow rate is caused by the consumption of steam (heavier gas) by oxidation, which produces H₂ (lighter gas), leading to a low mass flow rate. After a few hours, insufficient cooling causes a temperature increase, leading to further core degradation and complete meltdown. However, only in the BDBA4_120 case is a significant mass flow rate increase from around 150000 s (~41.5 h), suggesting increased vapor content in RPV by flow back from

the Containment and/or condensation confirmed in Fig. 12.

One can see that from around 72000 s (20 h) s to 150000 s (~41.5 h), there is nearly no steam flow in RCS Fig. 11 and Fig. 16, negligible or nonflow through RVV, Fig. 12. Within this period, at around 95000 s (26 h) there is an oxidation peak and final core degradation, after which all core materials are relocated to the lower plenum, and oxidation decreases, Fig. 9. While all core materials are in LP the RCS circulation is slowly cooling down the system (Fig. 6), and the oxidation of residual material slows down (consuming all available steam), up to 147000 s (~41 h) when it starts stopping. At that time, one can see significant changes in the RCS behavior, temperature drop, reestablishing RVV fluctuations, and steam pushed back to RPV as no more heat is generated from oxidation. It looks like the oxidation could not be maintained due to limited access to residual zirconium and steel in LP (there is still mass in LP) and cooling of RCS by circulation.

The whole system relies on the TH balance, which is based on relatively small differences in pressure and temperature and, in that case, also depends on mass accessibility. This observation confirms that modeling and simulating phenomena and systems governed by fragile TH balance is potentially challenging for SA codes as it could be affected by code limitations like averaging TH properties in CVH. It should be highlighted that this research should be continued by performing sensitivity and uncertainty analyses of this and similar cases, which will provide more details and understanding of iPWR simulations.

3.7. Ultimate heat sink

The next part of this analysis is focused on new features of integrated nuclear designs, like pressurized steel containment and the reactor pool. These features force changes in a safety simulation approach and analysis compared to a classic PWR where Containment is not submerged in the ultimate heat sink, which is the reactor pool, as it is in the iPWR design. This changes accident progression and phenomena's importance, e.g., risk related to H₂ due to lack of air in containment or source term. In an integral design, the Containment and reactor pool behavior is crucial for severe accident long-term mitigation, and the number of studies in that area is limited. A few main parameters related to these issues are presented and discussed here.

Containment assumed natural circulation patterns and circulation mass flow rates are presented respectively in Fig. 17, Fig. 18, Fig. 19 and Fig. 20. Note, that to improve readability of data (decrease fluctuations) Fig. 19 shows moving average for each ten data points not actual data values. Printed values are related to the bottom part of the Containment, where mainly water, circulates in the simulated scenarios, and the upper

part, occupied by steam, see Fig. 17 where the arrows indicate flow patterns. For the Containment, hot (red arrows) indicates control volumes or flow path connections from the RCS side, and cold (blue arrows) from the reactor pool side. Negative values in the integrated mass flow rate plots mean the flow is opposite to the defined flow path direction.

At the beginning of the accident, there was a major mass flow rate fluctuation from ~ -250 kg/s to more than 500 kg/s in the lower part of the Containment and from ~ -40 kg/s to 100 kg/s in the upper part of the Containment, see Fig. 18. These fluctuations are caused by rapid pressurization of the Containment and the high mass flow rate of the steam and water ejected through the break. The top part is filled by steam, which, due to lower density, causes a much lower mass flow rate in the upper part compared to the bottom part of the Containment. Next, the circulation stabilizes what can be seen as a stable mass flow rate. Fig. 18 and Fig. 19 one can notice that the flow disturbances occur in the upper Containment (steam) at the first oxidation, when peaks of mass flow rate could be noticed in BDBA4_120 case around 5 h. The mass flow rate fluctuations shown in Fig. 19 and Fig. 20 partially agree with the core degradation phase; however, in some cases, there is a small delay in the Containment and RP response caused by the thermal inertia of the simulated system. One example are BDBA2s cases, which in Fig. 19 shows an increased mass flow rate from 15 h when PCT and oxidation peaks occurred between 10–12 h.

The peaks in Fig. 20 (positive for the hot side, and negative for the cold side) are related to oxidation time and confirm a steam suction from Containment to the RPV. Comparing Fig. 18 and Fig. 19, one can see that the bottom and top parts of Containment behave differently, e.g., BDBA4_120 and BDBA3_120 cases show increased mass flow rate at the time when core degradation increases (respectively 12 and 22 h), in the

Fig. 17. Containment and reactor pool circulation patterns, not in scale.

Fig. 18. Circulation mass flow rate between Containment's hot side CVHs in the bottom on the left and upper part on the right.

Fig. 19. Circulation mass flow rate in the upper part of the Containment (zoomed and smoothed).

lower part but not in the upper part. This shows that circulation patterns for steam and liquid are independent and are impacted by different phenomena. In these cases, the core relocates to the lower plenum shortly before the peak, causing the temperature increase in the RPV and, consequently, Containment coolant. The circulation in the bottom part (water) is relatively stable until the end of the transient, except in the cases mentioned above, where it increases after core degradation.

Analyzing these issues provides important insights into iPWR severe accident simulations and will be considered for a follow-up study. It was shown that Containment natural circulation was established, and it may be disturbed by major accident events such as oxidation or corium relocation.

In Fig. 21 and Fig. 22, respectively, the temperatures of the containment vessel HS from inside (containment) and outside (reactor pool) are shown. The internal surface of the Containment is heated up directly after the break, and it is slowly cooled down for the next ~ 15 h. Analyzing the left and right sides of Fig. 21 (inner and outer side of the Containment), one can see a high temperature gradient, especially in the first 5 h. From 20 h till the end, temperature stabilizes and gradually increases in most cases. The most severe case, BDBA4_120, in which core degradation is divided into two phases (see Fig. 8), shows that the oxidation peaks and corium relocation impact the inside temperature of

Fig. 20. Circulation mass flow rate between upper Containment's CVHs, hot side on the left, and cold side on the right.

Fig. 21. Containment vessel temperature on the inner side (Containment) on the left and outer (RP) side on the right.

Fig. 22. Water temperature in the reactor pool.

the Containment vessel. The observed HS temperature fluctuation Fig. 21 corresponds, with some delay, to the progress of core degradation. A similar influence, but not as significant as in BDBA4_120, is noticeable for the BDBA2s where late oxidation occurs (between 11–15 h). The smooth and stretched in time temperature fluctuations (e.g., BDBA4_120 around 25 h) are probably related to the system’s thermal inertia and are expected.

The temperatures on the RP side of the Containment (right in Fig. 21) at the beginning of the transient behave similarly to the internal side, with a rapid increase, stabilization, and smooth temperature variation in the same cases mentioned before. The main difference is that it stabilizes not around constant value but linearly increases from 330 K (at 5 h) up to 369–378 K, depending on the case.

The temperature of the reactor pool water, Fig. 22, from the beginning of the accident till the end of the simulation, slowly increases from 320 K up to 363–373 K depending on the case (high decay heat, higher temperature). At the end of the simulations, two temperature clusters can be noticed; higher decay heat shows higher temperatures, which is more visible on the RP side of the Containment. The presented behavior is expected and simulated smoothly without numerical variations.

Fig. 23 presents the circulation mass flow rate between reactor pool control volumes exchanging heat with Containment; see Fig. 17. When the accident begins, a high mass flow rate occurs. After about 2–3 h, it

decreases for the next 15 h to around 700 kg/s. From that point, the cases with core degradation evolve similarly to Containment temperatures Fig. 21 as described in the previous paragraph.

The obtained results for pool temperature behavior look credible. This work will continue to investigate the effect of the flow paths and nodalization of the reactor pool, Containment, and reactor building on the results.

4. Conclusion

The work presented in this paper was done in the frame of the SASPAM-SA project as part of the WP2, “Input deck development and hypothetical SA scenarios assessment (SCENARIOS)” coordinated by KIT (Germany). The authors developed a generic iPWR input deck in MELCOR 2.2 and calculated hypothetical postulated severe accident scenarios. The work focused on: the identification of plausible SA scenarios for iPWR designs; and the identification of the conditions in the vessel and in the Containment that characterize iPWR SA scenarios and differ significantly from those in large-LWRs. The iPWR accident simulation shown in this paper provides general knowledge about MELCOR capabilities to model and simulate such designs and behavior of the integrated light water SMRs under accidental conditions.

In the analyzed scenarios, authors considered different break elevations and increased decay heat as sensitivity cases. However, all scenarios lead to similar accident progression in which water evacuates from the RPV to Containment, which, depending on the analyzed scenario, leads to complete, partial, or no core recovery. When the water level in RPV drops below the elevation of the lower support plate, the natural circulation of steam within RCS is established, which cools down the core. However, only in some cases the natural circulation can stop oxidation and further core degradation. The main differences between the analyzed scenarios are associated with the evolution of the RCS water level and circulation mass flow rate.

In the BDBA1 cases, with no core uncover, calculations did not enter severe accident conditions, and the scenario was fully mitigated. The BDBA2 cases where RCS stabilizes around the bottom of the core generate more H₂ than the other scenarios as they provide the most steam for oxidation. At the same time, natural circulation within RCS is blocked due to the remaining water in the reactor vessel.

The performed analyses provide insights into the iPWR SA analyses. For example, higher decay heat results in earlier and higher core degradation. In the long-term, pool and Containment conditions stabilize (stably heats up), cooling down RCS, and mitigating further degradation. Natural circulation phenomena seem to be adequately simulated, and besides relatively high fluctuations in some parts of the

Fig. 23. Circulation of the RP water between middle CVHs exchanging heat with Containment.

transients, the mass flow rate shows the expected behavior.

In the investigated iPWR concept, natural circulation is important to cool the core in accident situations, as there are no active systems or recirculation pumps. In SA codes such as MELCOR, proper nodalization and input deck definition are crucial for appropriately simulating accident progression, especially where passive safety systems and natural circulation play major roles during the transient (lack of active systems). The applied input deck nodalization was able to finalize a wide variety of scenario calculations, proving that it could be considered a stable background for further (best practice) development of iPWR SA calculations. The steam and H₂ circulation differences discussed in the paper highlight the significance of the natural circulation phenomena, as relatively small changes in the input deck and/or scenario assumptions lead to visible differences in the results.

The obtained results present insights that could help inform future iPWR severe accident analyses and decrease potential uncertainties. The most interesting insights are sensitivity to decay heat and circulation patterns in RPV, Containment, and between these two vessels. The authors believe that the results motivate further work on this topic as it is essential to enhance understanding of potential code challenges and input deck performance, which will help develop best practices for the iPWR modeling.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Grammarly in order to improve the language correctness and clarity of the message. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

M. Malicki: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **T. Lind:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments & Disclaimer

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation(SERI).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission-Euratom. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

References

- ASTEC code DBA analysis of a passive mitigation strategy on a generic IRIS SMR, Pietro Maccari, Fulvio Mascari, Stefano Ederli, Paride Meloni, Sandro Manservigi, *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, Volume 156, 15 June 2021, 108194 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2021.108194>.
- Campbell, S., Esmaili, H., Schaperow, J., 2019, Independent MELCOR Confirmatory Analysis for NuScale Small Modular Reactor, Fuel and Source Term Code Development Branch Division of Systems Analysis Office of Nuclear Regulatory Research United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2019, RES/FSCB 2019-01.
- Fakhraei, A., 2021. Coolant flow rate instability during extended station blackout accident in NuScale SMR: Two approaches for improving flow stability. *Prog. Nucl. Energy* 131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2020.103602>.
- Hosseini, Seyed Ali, Reza Akbari, Amir Saeed Shirani, Francesco D'Auria, 2021. Analysis of the natural circulation flow map uncertainties in an integral small modular reactor. *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, 378, 111156, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2021.111156>.
- Humphries, L.L., Beeny, B.A., Gelbard, F., Louie, D.L., Phillips, J., 2019. "MELCOR Computer – Code Manuals", Vol 1: User Manual, Version 2.2.14959, October 2019.
- Humphries, L.L., Beeny, B.A., Gelbard, F., Louie, D.L., Phillips, J., 2019. "MELCOR Computer – Code Manuals", Vol 2: Reference Manual, Version 2.2.14959, October 2019.

- Humphries, L., 2017, "MELCOR Code Development Status – EMUG 2017" Sandia National Laboratories, (https://www.psi.ch/sites/default/files/import/emug/Emug2017EN/EMUG_2017_01.pdf, accessed 12 April 2024).
- L. Humphries, 2018, MELCOR Code Development Status – EMUG 2018, Sandia National Laboratories, (https://www.psi.ch/sites/default/files/import/emug/Emug2018EN/EMUG_2018_01.pdf, accessed 12 April 2024).
- Humpriesa, L., Gauntt, R.O., 2018, MELCOR 2.2 Severe Accident Analysis Code – Current Status And Plans For Future, Sandia National Laboratories, 2018. available online (<https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1513446-melcor-severe-accident-analysis-code-current-status-plans-future>) (accessed 12 April 2024).
- IAEA, 2022, Advances in Small Modular Reactor Technology Developments A Supplement to:IAEA Advanced Reactors Information System (ARIS) 2022 Edition, September 2022.
- Kima, J., Jung, G., Kim, H., 2011. Severe Accident Analysis of SBLOCA sequences for SMART using MELCOR code. Transactions of the Korean Nuclear Society Spring Meeting Taebaek.
- Lebel, L., Morreale, A., Batten, K., Clouthier, T., 2022. Aerosol retention within submerged Containment-Type iPWRs: Experiments and modeling. Nucl. Eng. Des. 398, 111994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2022.111994>.
- Li, L., et al., 2017. MELCOR severe accident analysis for a natural circulation small modular reactor. Prog. Nucl. Energy 100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2017.06.003>.
- Lin, Y., Gao, P., Chen, X., Bello, S., Tian, C., Zhao, C., 2021. Experimental investigation on instability characteristics of loss of heat sink accident in a natural circulation system. Ann. Nucl. Energy 155 (1), 108143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2021.108143>.
- Malicki, M., Lind, T., MELCOR 2.2 iPWR LOCA type accident analysis, PART I: thermal-hydraulics, Nuclear Engineering and Design.
- Malicki, M., Darnowski, P., Lind, T., 2024. An iPWR MELCOR 2.2 Study on the Impact of the Modeling Parameters on Code Performance and Accident Progression, Energies, 17(13), 3279; <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17133279>.
- Mascari, F., 2022. Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation strategies – Severe Accident (SASPAM-SA) Horizon Euratom Project, ETSON NEWS, September 2022, <https://www.etsn.eu/node/290> (accessed 12 April 2024).
- Qiu, Jinrong, Li, Longze, Tai, Yun, Shiwei Yao, Su, G.H., Suizheng Qiu, 2020. MELCOR simulation of the SBLOCA induced severe accident for the SMR in a floating nuclear power plant, Progress in Nuclear Energy 129 (2020) 103509, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2020.103509>.
- Qiu, Z., Hongxing, Yu., Xiong, Q., Cao, X., Tong, L., 2023. Uncertainty and sensitivity analysis of the DVI line break loss of coolant accident for small modular reactor. Prog. Nucl. Energy 157, 104575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2023.104575>.
- Reyes Jr, J.N., 2011. NuScale plant safety in response to extreme events. Nucl. Technol. 2017. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT12-A13556>.
- Ross, K., Phillips, J., Gauntt, R. O., Wagner, K. C., 2014, MELCOR Best Practices as Applied in the State-of-the-Art Reactor Consequence Analyses (SOARCA) Project, NUREG/CR-7008, 2014.
- Santinello, M., Ricotti, M., 2018. Preliminary analysis of an integral small modular reactor operating in a submerged containment. Prog. Nucl. Energy 107, 90–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2018.04.013>.
- Santinello, M., Ricotti, M.E., Ninokata, H., Haraty, G., Ingremeau, J.J., Gourmel, V., 2017. External heat transfer capability of a submerged SMR containment: The Flexblue case. Prog Nucl. Energy 96, 62–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2016.12.002>.
- SASPAM-SA, "Milestone 2.1: Generic Data on Design 1 and Design 2" (2023).
- Small Modular Reactors: Challenges and Opportunities, OECD 2021, NEA No. 7560, Nuclear energy agency organization for economic co-operation and development, https://www.oecd-nea.org/upload/docs/application/pdf/2021-03/7560_smr_report.pdf (accessed 12 April 2024).
- SMR Regulators' Forum, Pilot Project Report: Considering the Application of a Graded Approach, Defence-in-Depth and Emergency Planning Zone Size for Small Modular Reactors, January 2018.
- Yifan, Xu, Peng, M., Xia, G., Shang, H.e., 2021. Optimization of forced circulation to natural circulation transition characteristics of IPWR. Ann. Nucl. Energy 157, 108249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2021.108249>.
- Zhao, Y., Peng, M., Xia, G., 2020. Safety evaluation of the flashing-driven natural circulation IPWR against Loss-of-Feedwater accident. Ann. Nucl. Energy 142, 107408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2020.107408>.